

A new operator that combines artificial immune systems and multi-agent systems for addressing flow shop scheduling problems

Um novo operador que combina sistemas imunológicos artificiais e sistemas multiagentes para resolver problemas de agendamento de flow shop

Un nuevo operador que combina sistemas inmunológicos artificiales y sistemas multiagente para abordar los problemas de programación del taller de flujo

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ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a novel mutation operator that integrates concepts from artificial immune systems and multi-agent systems to enhance systematic preventive maintenance policies within hybrid flow shop scheduling. The mutation operator is designed to make slight adjustments to the sequence, generating a new yet similar sequence. Its primary goal is to prevent convergence to a local optimum and to increase diversity within the population. Additionally, the mutation operator can be viewed as a straightforward form of local search. The proposed method draws inspiration from human body behavior, leading to the implementation of a problem-solving strategy focused on optimizing processing time through metaheuristic techniques. This approach combines multi-agent systems with elements inspired by the artificial immune system. The effectiveness of our method is consistently demonstrated throughout the paper. We apply this approach to three preventive maintenance policies aimed at maximizing availability and maintaining a minimum level of reliability in the production chain. The results indicate that our algorithm surpasses existing algorithms, taking into account the potential periodic unavailability of machines during production scheduling.

Keywords: hybrid flow shop scheduling, artificial immune system, mutation operator, multi agent systems, makespan.

RESUMO

Este artigo apresenta um novo operador de mutação que integra conceitos de sistemas imunológicos artificiais e sistemas multiagentes para aprimorar políticas sistemáticas de

manutenção preventiva dentro do agendamento de flow shop híbrido. O operador de mutação é projetado para fazer pequenos ajustes na sequência, gerando uma sequência nova, porém semelhante. O seu principal objetivo é evitar a convergência para um ótimo local e aumentar a diversidade da população. Além disso, o operador de mutação pode ser visto como uma forma direta de busca local. O método proposto inspira-se no comportamento do corpo humano, levando à implementação de uma estratégia de resolução de problemas focada na otimização do tempo de processamento através de técnicas metaheurísticas. Esta abordagem combina sistemas multiagentes com elementos inspirados no sistema imunológico artificial. A eficácia do nosso método é demonstrada consistentemente ao longo do artigo. Aplicamos esta abordagem a três políticas de manutenção preventiva que visam maximizar a disponibilidade e manter um nível mínimo de confiabilidade na cadeia produtiva. Os resultados indicam que nosso algoritmo supera os algoritmos existentes, levando em consideração a potencial indisponibilidade periódica das máquinas durante a programação da produção.

Palavras-chave: agendamento de flow shop híbrido, sistema imunológico artificial, operador de mutação, sistemas multiagentes, makespan.

RESUMEN

Este artículo presenta un nuevo operador de mutación que integra conceptos de sistemas inmunológicos artificiales y sistemas de múltiples agentes para mejorar las políticas sistemáticas de mantenimiento preventivo dentro de la programación del taller de flujo híbrido. El operador de mutación está diseñado para realizar ligeros ajustes en la secuencia, generando una secuencia nueva pero similar. Su objetivo principal es evitar la convergencia hacia un óptimo local y aumentar la diversidad dentro de la población. Además, el operador de mutación puede verse como una forma sencilla de búsqueda local. El método propuesto se inspira en el comportamiento del cuerpo humano y conduce a la implementación de una estrategia de resolución de problemas centrada en optimizar el tiempo de procesamiento mediante técnicas metaheurísticas. Este enfoque combina sistemas multiagente con elementos inspirados en el sistema inmunológico artificial. La eficacia de nuestro método se demuestra consistentemente a lo largo del artículo. Aplicamos este enfoque a tres políticas de mantenimiento preventivo encaminadas a maximizar la disponibilidad y mantener un nivel mínimo de confiabilidad en la cadena de producción. Los resultados indican que nuestro algoritmo supera a los algoritmos existentes, teniendo en cuenta la posible indisponibilidad periódica de las máquinas durante la programación de la producción.

Palabras clave: programación de taller de flujo híbrido, sistema inmunológico artificial, operador de mutaciones, sistemas multiagente, makespan.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the key assumptions in scheduling studies is that machines may not be periodically available during production. While many researchers have sought to integrate production and preventive maintenance planning using various methods, some of these approaches are so complex that they cannot be independently coded to achieve the same level of effectiveness. Additionally, some widely-used methods have specific functionalities

that do not easily extend to other problems.

This paper proposes the application of a new mutation operator inspired by artificial immune systems and multi-agent systems to integrate systematic preventive maintenance policies within hybrid flow shop scheduling. The aim is to minimize execution time. To address this challenge, a multi-agent system based on the artificial immune system, along with several constructive heuristics, has been developed.

2 RELATED WORK

Numerous realistic assumptions have been integrated into scheduling problems. For instance, due to the interplay between production and maintenance activities, many researchers have focused on jointly planning these two aspects. (Dabiri, 2022) demonstrate that the Flow Shop problem with downtime on a single machine is NP-hard. (Benda, 2019) investigates scheduling in a flow shop with availability constraints (SFSAC) and examines two variants of non-preemptive SFSAC: one where maintenance activity start times are fixed, and another where these times are flexible. He employs a genetic algorithm and tabu search to address the problem. (Tadayonirad, 2019) explore non-preemptive scheduling in a two-stage flow shop with one machine at the first stage and multiple machines at the second stage, aiming to minimize execution time. They assume each machine has a known lockup period in advance and analyze the worst-case performance of three other heuristics. (Costa, 2017) aims to integrate single machine scheduling with preventive maintenance planning, developing a genetic algorithm based on the integrated model proposed by (Wang, 2016). (Wu, 2015) examine a two-machine flow shop scenario with possible downtimes on one machine, proving that minimizing makespan is strongly NP-hard. (Bentaleb, 2019) tackles the scheduling of n preemptive jobs in a two-machine flow shop where the first machine is unavailable for processing during a specified time interval. (Hu, 2016) studies the problem involving stochastic machine breakdowns and separated time settings. (Mosheiov, 2018) consider a two-machine flow shop requiring maintenance activities to occur after a fixed number of jobs, with the durations of these maintenance tasks being constant. Lastly, (Chen, 2021) surveys existing methods for solving scheduling problems under availability constraints and discusses the complexity of the outcomes.

3 RELATED WOR HYBRID FLOW SHOP SCHEDULING

The hybrid flow shop scheduling problem (HFSP) can be described as follows:

consider a set of n jobs to be processed across m stages. Each stage i can have multiple identical machines operating in parallel, denoted as m_i . In HFSP, all jobs must follow the same order through the stages, starting from stage 1 to stage m . Each job can be handled by any machine within a single stage, but once assigned to a machine, the process cannot be interrupted.

Additionally, each machine can only handle one job at a time, and there are no precedence constraints between jobs, allowing them to be processed in any order. The processing time for each job j at stage i (denoted as $P_{j,i}$) is fixed and predetermined. Since the machines are identical, the processing time for a job remains constant across machines at each stage. In HFSP, there are two key decision dimensions:

- ✓ Job sequencing
- ✓ Job assignment to machines at each stage.

Figure. 1 illustrates a diagram of a hybrid flow shop setup.

Source: (Chen, 2021)

4 TECHNIQUES FOR SOLVING FLOW SHOP SCHEDULING PROBLEMS

Minimizing the makespan in the case of general flow shop is NP-hard in the strong sense. Several heuristics have been proposed to solve it, and especially that Exact Algorithms, Heuristic Methods and Metaheuristic Approaches. Each of these heuristics gives good results, but no guarantees the optimal solution.

4.1 EXACT ALGORITHMS

- **Branch and Bound:** Systematically explores all possible schedules, pruning branches that exceed known bounds.
- **Dynamic Programming:** Breaks down the problem into simpler subproblems and solves them recursively.

- **Integer Linear Programming (ILP):** Formulates the scheduling problem as a linear program with integer constraints.

4.2 HEURISTIC METHODS

- **Priority Dispatching Rules:** Uses rules like First-Come-First-Served (FCFS), Shortest Processing Time (SPT), or Earliest Due Date (EDD) to generate schedules quickly.
- **Insertion Heuristics:** Starts with an initial schedule and iteratively inserts jobs in the optimal position to improve the makespan.

4.3 METAHEURISTIC APPROACHES

- **Genetic Algorithms (GA):** Uses principles of natural selection to evolve solutions over generations.
- **Simulated Annealing (SA):** Mimics the annealing process in metallurgy to escape local optima and explore the solution space.
- **Tabu Search:** Maintains a list of previously visited solutions to avoid cycling back and promotes exploration of new areas.

4.4 HYBRID TECHNIQUES

- **Combining Heuristics and Metaheuristics:** Integrates fast heuristic methods with metaheuristics to enhance solution quality and speed.
- **Multi-Objective Optimization:** Simultaneously optimizes multiple objectives (e.g., makespan, total tardiness) using techniques like Pareto optimization.

4.5 SCHEDULING ALGORITHMS

- **Two-Stage Flow Shop Algorithms:** Specialized algorithms designed specifically for two-stage flow shop scenarios.
- **Branch-and-Price:** Combines branch-and-bound with pricing to solve large-scale instances effectively.

4.6 ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE APPROACHES

- **Reinforcement Learning:** Employs learning algorithms that can adapt and optimize scheduling decisions over time based on feedback.
- **Neural Networks:** Uses deep learning to model complex relationships in scheduling problems, potentially learning optimal schedules from data.

4.7 SIMULATION-BASED APPROACHES

- **Discrete Event Simulation:** Models the flow of jobs through the shop and evaluates different scheduling policies based on simulated performance.

5 LIMITATIONS OF EXISTING METHODS

Despite the availability of numerous methods, such as mathematical programming, various criteria, and heuristics for integrating production scheduling and maintenance, many of these approaches have significant limitations. For instance, the methods proposed are often overly complex and necessitate extensive coding efforts for implementation. Exact methods are impractical for small instances (typically up to 10-15 jobs), and even in such cases, the computation time can be exceedingly high.

6 MULTI-AGENT SYSTEM AND ARTIFICIAL IMMUNE SYSTEM APPROACH (MASAIS)

In our proposed approach, MASAIS, antigens represent the objective function (makespan) that needs to be optimized, while antibodies correspond to candidate solutions. This approach is based on clonal selection and is particularly inspired by the CLONALG algorithm. Additionally, MASAIS incorporates the principle of affinity maturation from the immune system.

The AIS begins with a population of antibodies, which are then refined through a series of operators until a stopping criterion is met. An iteration of the AIS to generate the next population can be outlined as follows:

- ✓ First, an acceleration mechanism is applied, allowing candidates with superior solution quality to be carried over to the next population.
- ✓ The remaining antibodies in the new population are enhanced through mutation and crossover operators.

- ✓ A selection function is used to determine which antibodies will undergo these operations, incorporating both the value of each antibody and an affinity calculation.
- ✓ Candidate solutions with better objective function values are assigned higher probabilities of selection to produce the next generation of solutions.
- ✓ This mechanism ensures that the new generation consists largely of candidate solutions with favorable properties.

Conversely, the affinity calculations between antibodies help eliminate similar candidates. The process involves the following steps:

If a candidate solution exceeds a specified affinity threshold (AT), its probability of selection is reduced by multiplying its prior probability (derived from its performance) by a lower factor known as Affinity Adjustment (AA). This adjustment decreases its chances of being selected.

6.1 FLOWCHART OF OUR MAS AIS APPROACH

Figure. 2 presents a detailed flowchart of our SMAAIS approach for integrating maintenance policies into hybrid flow shop scheduling. In our method, each agent follows the same process to calculate the objective function (Fitness), which in this case corresponds to the makespan value. The operations carried out by each agent include:

- ✓ Generating a set of antibodies (TP) as the initial population.
- ✓ Evaluating the quality of the antibodies.
- ✓ Computing the affinity values of the antibodies.
- ✓ Implementing an acceleration mechanism.
- ✓ Selecting two parent solutions using a selection mechanism.
- ✓ Performing uniform crossover.
- ✓ Applying point mutation.

This process is repeated until an agent achieves the lowest fitness value.

Figure 2. Flowchart of our MAS AIS approach

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

6.2 CODING SCHEME AND OPERATORS OF MAS AIS

6.2.1 Initialization

- **Parameter Setting:** Define the population size (TP), the number of solutions directly copied to the next generation (Nr), the mutation probability (Pm), the weights for similarity factors (W1, W2, W3, W4), the affinity threshold (AT), and the affinity adjustment (AA).

- Initial Population Generation:

- ✓ Randomly create an initial population of (TP-4) antibodies.
- ✓ Generate antibodies using Branch and Bound.
- ✓ Generate antibodies using SPT.
- ✓ Generate antibodies based on Genetic Algorithm.
- ✓ Generate antibodies using Reinforcement Learning.

6.2.2 Random Key Algorithm

The coding scheme employs a random key (RK) representation, initially proposed by (Fayyazi, 2015) for problems involving multiple identical machines and subsequently utilized in studies (Zandieh, 2020).

The most important advantages of this type of coding scheme are to be simple to implement and easily adaptable to all operators. It could be described as follows:

Table 1. Random Key Algorithm

Random Key Algorithm
<p>For Each Job Do Assign a real number where the integer part is the machine number to which the Job is assigned. The fractional part is used to control the Jobs assigned to each machine. Random numbers are used only for the first stage. They determine the Job sequence and assignment only for stage 1.</p> <p>For all subsequent stages $i, \{i = 2, 3, \dots, m\}$ Do The Job sequence is determined by the latest completion times of the Jobs in the previous stage. The machine assignment rule is the first available machine.</p> <p>End For End For</p>

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

For our analysis, we generate four random numbers from a uniform distribution ranging from 1 to $1+m1 + m1 + m1$ for the first stage, as illustrated in Figure. 3.

Figure 3. Encoded solution represented in CK format.

2,76	1,46	2,53	1,72
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Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

It is well established that initial solutions can significantly impact the final results achieved by the AIS. Consequently, we generated the initial solutions as follows: four solutions were created using the heuristics Branch and Bound, SPT, Genetic Algorithm, and Reinforcement Learning, while the remaining solutions were generated randomly.

Chromosomes with lower makespan values are preferred, so a number of chromosomes (Nr) with the lowest makespan are automatically retained for the next generation. This process is referred to as reproduction. The remaining chromosomes, calculated as $(TP - Nr)\%$, are produced by combining two other sequences or relatives using a crossover operator. It is essential that the crossover operators avoid generating infeasible solutions.

6.2.3 Selection process Algorithm

To select parents for crossover, we employ a classification selection method, which can be described as follows:

Table 2. Classement Selection process Algorithm

Classement Selection process Algorithm
The individuals of the current population are first sorted based on their objective functions.
For Each individual Do
Assign a normalized probability such that the best solutions are more likely to be selected.
End For
The individuals are randomly chosen as parents to undergo operators based on their probabilities.

Source: Prepared by the authors

6.2.4 Uniform crossover set

The aim is to produce improved offspring, meaning to create better sequences by merging the parents. We use a uniform crossover set (UCS), which has demonstrated its effectiveness in HFSP in previous studies (Zandieh, 2020). It is important to note that UCS operates with random keys and is defined as follows:

This procedure is numerically illustrated using an example with ($n = 5$) and ($m1 = 2$), as shown in Figure. 4.

Figure .4 UCS illustrated with an example where $n=5$ and $m1=2$

Parent 1	2,77	1,48	2,72	1,33	2,86
Parent 2	1,32	2,79	2,27	1,96	2,59
Rand N°	0,52	0,37	0,86	0,32	0,79
Children	2,77	1,48	2,72	1,33	2,59

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

6.2.5 Single point mutation

A mutation operator is employed to modify the sequence, generating a new yet similar sequence. The primary goal of mutation is to prevent convergence to a local optimum and to promote population diversity. The mutation operator can also be viewed as a straightforward method of local search.

Numerous studies have shown that single point mutation (SPM) often yields better results compared to other mutation types, such as SWAP or inversion. Consequently, we utilize the SPM mutation (Brito, 2022). The SPM can be described as follows:

A random job a is selected, and its random key (RK) is regenerated. Figure. 5 illustrates a solution that undergoes mutation.

Figure .5 Procedure for single point mutation illustrated with an example where n=5 and m1=2.

Before Mutation	1,73	2,58	1,92	2,33	2,66
After Mutation	1,73	1,88	1,92	2,33	2,66

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

6.2.6 Objective Function

Generally, an objective function (Fitness) encompasses one or more performance indicators that assess the effectiveness of an antibody.

First, the antibody candidates are transformed into a valid scheduling format. They are then evaluated using an objective function to determine their fitness values. In maximization problems, a higher fitness value is preferred, and the AIS aims to maximize it.

For minimization problems, the objective function is structured to convert it into a maximization problem. In our scenario, the goal is to minimize makespan; thus, a candidate solution with a high makespan is assigned a low fitness value.

The fitness function for an antibody *i* is calculated as follows:

Table 3. Objective Function

Objective Function
<p>For each Job j Do Calculate a similarity ratio. End For The average of the ratios for all the jobs in an antibody is defined as the overall affinity value of that antibody. The similarity ratio of job <i>j</i> is calculated by comparing the position of this job with the corresponding antibody and APC.</p>

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

$$f(i) = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^{TP} \frac{1}{C_{max}(i)}} \quad (1)$$

where

f (*i*) is the fitness value for the antibody *I*, *C*_{max} (*i*) is the makespan for the antibody *i* and *TP*: is the size of population.

Where *f*(*i*) represents the fitness value for antibody *I*, *C*_{max}(*i*) denotes the makespan for antibody *i*, and *TP* refers to the population size.

6.2.7 Affinity

Based on the calculated probabilities and the associated affinity values, selection is conducted using a ranking mechanism. To further assess the effectiveness of the affinity function in the AIS, we also implemented uniform crossover and single point mutation.

The evaluation of affinity in the AIS enhances the diversity of antibodies within the population, allowing for more extensive exploration of the search space, albeit at the cost of increased computation time.

The key consideration is whether, in such a complex problem, the calculation of affinity incurs a significant cost, specifically in terms of the time it contributes to the overall computation time of the algorithm. In the following section, we will detail the affinity calculation procedure.

6.2.8 Affinity Calculation Algorithm

To determine affinity, antibodies are compared with the best-known antibody (BKA) obtained to date. Affinity reflects the similarity between an antibody and the BKA.

In this context, the theory of entropy is employed to estimate the probability of recurrence of a given information element. (Mosheiov, 2018) defines the information entropy, $H(x)$, of a discrete random variable $X=\{x_1,x_2,\dots,x_n\}$ with a probability mass function $P(X=x)=p_i, i=1,2,\dots,N$ as follows:

$$H(x) = -\sum_{i=1}^n p_i \log(p_i) \quad (2)$$

The application of information entropy allows us to express the similarity of antibody i (or sequence i) in relation to a reference antibody (or sequence) as follows:

$$aff(i) = \frac{1}{1+\frac{1}{k}\sum_{j=1}^k h_{ij}} \quad (3)$$

where

$aff(i)$ represents the similarity measure, k is the population size, and $h_{ij} = -p_{ij} \log(p_{ij})$

The affinity of each antibody in our problem is calculated as follows:

Table 4. Affinity Calculation Algorithm

Affinity Calculation Algorithm
<p>For each Job j Do Calculate a similarity ratio. End For</p> <p>The average of the ratios for all the jobs in an antibody is defined as the overall affinity value of that antibody.</p> <p>The similarity ratio for job j is calculated by comparing the position of this job with the corresponding antibody and APC.</p> <p>The Job sequence and assignment for subsequent stages are obtained using the following rules:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The latest completion time of the Jobs in the previous stage and the first available machine, respectively. - The similarity ratio is obtained from the position of Job j in stage 1.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

Each criterion has a weight that reflects its relative importance (denoted by W_i , where $i = \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$). When a criterion is met, job j is assigned its corresponding weight, and the total value of the weights represents the similarity ratio for job j . After calculating the similarity for each job, the average similarities of the jobs are used to determine the affinity of the antibody candidate.

7 ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

In this section, we evaluate the proposed multi-agent approach based on the artificial immune system. The goal is to compare our method with several other approaches, including heuristics, Branch and Bound, SPT, Genetic Algorithm, and Reinforcement Learning. We implemented these heuristics in MATLAB 7.0, running on a PC with an Intel Core 2 Duo 2.0 GHz processor and 2 GB of RAM. The stopping criterion used for testing all heuristic instances is set to a CPU time limit of $n \times m \times 1.5$ milliseconds. This criterion is designed to be sensitive not only to the number of jobs but also to the number of stages. The relative percentage deviation (RPD) is used as the performance measure to compare the methods. The optimal solution for each instance, referred to as Min_{sol} , is calculated using an algorithm. RPD is then calculated using the following formula (4):

$$RPD = \frac{Alg_{sol} - Min_{sol}}{Min_{sol}} \times 100 \quad (4)$$

Alg_{sol} represents the value of the objective function obtained for a specific algorithm and instance. Clearly, lower RPD values are preferred.

7.1 CONFIGURING THE PARAMETERS

It is well established that varying parameter levels significantly impact the quality of the solutions produced by our MAS AIS approach. We applied a set of parameters, including population size (SP), the number of solutions directly copied to the next population (Nr), mutation probability (Pm), similarity factor weights (W1, W2, W3, W4), the affinity threshold (AT), and affinity adjustment (AA). The parameter levels considered are presented in Table. 5.

Table 5. MAS AIS Parameter Settings

Parameters	N° of Level	Levels
Population Size	3	70, 120, 180
(Nr, Pm)	3	(1, 0.15), (2, 0.25), (3, 0.30)
(W1, W2, W3, W4)	2	(0.25, 0.15, 0.40, 0.40), (0.35, 0.25, 0.30, 0.30)
(AT, AA)	3	(0.45, 0.55), (0.65, 0.55), (0.85, 0.55)

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

A set of 40 patients is divided into 3 groups (n = 70,120, 180) and solved using the algorithms. After analyzing the results of SMAAIS, we selected the following parameters: Nr = 30, Pm = 0.25, TP = 180, W1 = 0.35, W2 = 0.25, W3 = 0.15, W4 = 0.15, AT = 0.65, and AA = 0.55. Specifically, if the affinity value exceeds 0.65, the probability of selection by the rating mechanism is multiplied by 0.55.

7.2 DATA COLLECTION

The data required to solve this problem is divided into two parts: production scheduling data and preventive maintenance (PM) data. To ensure efficient processing, the data must be organized in such a way that a large number of operations can be performed on each machine during PM. If the time between two consecutive PM operations is shorter than the maximum allowable processing time, it may not be possible to process all jobs. Conversely, if the time between operations is too long, it is likely that no PM operation will be needed at all.

The first part of the data includes the number of jobs (n), the number of stages (m), the number of identical machines at each stage (mi), the range of processing times (Pj,i), and the time constraints. We consider three values for the number of jobs: $n = \{70, 120, 180\}$, and for the number of stages, we use $m = \{3, 6, 9\}$. For the number of machines at each stage, we use two scenarios: in the first, the number of machines per stage is randomly distributed between one and three, while in the second; each stage is fixed with two

machines. The ready time for stage 1 is set to 0.

For all jobs, the ready time for stage (i + 1) corresponds to the execution time at stage i, so this data does not need to be generated. Table. 6 presents the factors and their corresponding levels.

Table 6. MASAIS Parameter and Level

Parameters	Levels
Job Number	70, 120, 180
Stages Number	3, 6, 9
Machine Distribution	a. Constant : 1 b. Variable : U (1, 3)
Duration Processing	U (1, 100)

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

The second section of the data is divided into three parts, each focusing on a different policy. As previously mentioned, the generation of TPMF, TPMop, and TPM must be carried out with great precision. To achieve this, we introduce an auxiliary variable, "xi," which is used to estimate the workload on the machines at each stage i, as follows:

$$x_i \approx \frac{n}{m_i} \tag{5}$$

Thus, "xi" represents the expected number of jobs on each machine at stage i. Consequently, the range of this variable is defined as follows:

$$x_i = \{11, 14.4, 18.5, 22, 25.3, 27, 35.3, 38, 42, 55, 80, 120\}$$

For example, when n=70, g=2, and m1=m2=2 and 3, the values of x1 = x2 are calculated as 35 and 23.3, respectively. The data required for each policy are generated as follows:

1. **Policy I for PM (TPMF):** The TPMF is determined based on xi . If xi<35, then TPMF = 550; otherwise, TPMF = 750. The duration of the PM operation (DPM) is set to 50%, 100%, and 150% of the processing time.
2. **Policy II for PM:** As previously mentioned, there are nine combinations of n and g. For each combination, β is defined as {3, 4, 5}. DPM remains the same as in Policy I. In this policy, tp is set to 2 and 9 rpm for all experiments. The values of θ are chosen based on xi to ensure a sufficient number of transactions are carried out on each PM machine. For instance, a small value of θ leads to a very large TPMop, which

could potentially prevent some jobs from being processed on the machines without interruptions, due to insufficient T_{PMop} .

3. **Policy III for PM:** The levels of θ , β and D_{PM} are the same as in Policy II. The objective is to achieve 90% production by time t , so $R_0(t)=0.85$. To calculate T_{PM} , the time t must be determined, which can be derived from the processing time of a given instance. Since processing times are uniformly distributed between 1 and 100, $t=x_i*50$.

The results for the different factor levels are summarized in 80, 180, and 180 scenarios for Policies I, II, and III, respectively. Each scenario consists of 10 distinct problems, leading to a total of 800, 1800, and 1800 instances, respectively.

7.3 RESULTS OF THE EXPERIMENTS

The results of experiments, averaged for each combination of n and m (with 180 data points per mean), are summarized in Tables 7, 8, and 9 for the three subsets (Policy I, II, and III). As anticipated, metaheuristic algorithms outperform heuristics across all three policies. The proposed SMASIA yields better results than the three Maintenance political, with a PRE of 1.71%, 1.64%, and 1.53% for Policies I, II, and III, respectively. In comparison, R_LEAR achieves a PRE of 3.59%, 3.29%, and 3.73% for Policies I, II, and III, respectively, while GA results in a RPD of 7.32%, 7.73%, and 7.56% for the same policies. Notably, the PRE results for SMASIA remain consistent across all 9 groups (combinations of n and m) and demonstrate its robust performance across the three MP policies.

Table 7. Mean RPD for the algorithms categorized by N and M under Policy I

n	m	Algorithms				
		MASAIS	R_LEAR	GA	SPT	BBOUND
70	3	1.85	3.29	9.79	30.59	32.51
	6	2.96	4.58	8.86	24.53	30.21
	9	1.47	3.42	8.55	31.49	27.55
120	3	1.83	2.51	7.39	28.21	30.36
	6	1.89	4.55	7.70	21.32	28.81
	9	1.48	2.78	9.21	25.20	30.16
180	3	1.32	3.38	4.58	24.27	26.42
	6	2.57	3.22	5.67	31.18	30.89
	9	1.26	3.42	4.81	27.28	25.42
Average		1.71	3.59	7.32	27.48	29.23

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

Table 8. Mean RPD for the algorithms categorized by N and M under Policy II

n	m	Algorithms				
		MASAIS	R_LEAR	GA	SPT	BBOUND
70	3	2.16	3.57	8.68	27.55	31.75
	6	1.26	2.13	9.63	28.68	28.95
	9	1.61	4.42	8.79	28.46	28.87
120	3	2.55	3.27	7.76	24.21	25.74
	6	1.75	3.32	8.34	28.29	31.82
	9	1.40	2.42	7.40	25.14	29.74
180	3	2.39	3.01	6.41	27.47	27.75
	6	1.41	3.20	5.12	26.27	31.30
	9	1.74	3.24	5.52	26.67	26.64
Average		1.64	3.29	7.73	26.69	29.17

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

Table 9. Mean RPD for the algorithms categorized by N and M under Policy III

n	m	Algorithms				
		MASAIS	R_LEAR	GA	SPT	BBOUND
70	3	2.38	3.32	8.74	26.99	29.72
	6	1.18	2.99	7.36	24.01	25.39
	9	1.21	3.29	8.37	27.69	32.26
120	3	1.40	4.23	9.59	28.18	25.24
	6	2.11	3.67	8.88	27.80	29.37
	9	1.01	4.49	9.40	29.32	30.92
180	3	2.38	2.40	5.34	27.13	32.27
	6	1.18	3.94	4.36	30.44	30.64
	9	2.16	4.34	5.13	31.70	28.33
Average		1.53	3.73	7.56	28.34	29.72

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

As observed, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) significantly outperforms the other heuristics, with Relative Percentage Deviations (RPD) of 7.32%, 7.73%, and 7.56% for policies I, II, and III, respectively. Following GA, the Shortest Processing Time (SPT) heuristic yields RPD values of 27.48%, 26.69%, and 28.34% for policies I, II, and III. The poorest-performing algorithm is BBOUND, with an RPD close to 30%. Figure 6 presents the mean results and Least Significant Difference (LSD) intervals for the algorithms, highlighting statistically significant differences in their performances. As shown in Figure 6, the proposed MASAIS algorithm delivers strong results compared to the other methods.

Figure .6 RPD mean values and LSD intervals (at 95% confidence) for different algorithm types.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

We examine the interactions between factors such as the number of jobs, number of stages, and policy type on the performance of the PM algorithm. In the conclusion, we summarize how the RPD values from the algorithms vary across different factor levels. Due to BBOUND's significantly lower performance, we exclude it from the analysis. Figures 7, 8, and 9 present the mean graphs showing the interactions between the metaheuristic algorithms and the different factors.

Figure .7 The RPD graph represents the interaction between metaheuristic algorithms and the number of jobs factor.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

Figure .8 RPD graph showing the interaction between metaheuristic algorithms and the number of stages factor.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

Figure .9 RPD graph illustrating the interaction between metaheuristic algorithms and the PM policies factor.

Source: Prepared by the authors, 2024

MAS AIS achieves the lowest RPD across all three levels of the number of jobs. As the number of jobs increases, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) becomes more efficient. Likewise, a higher number of stages leads to improved performance for GA. There is no significant interaction between algorithm performance and PM policies. In all scenarios, MAS AIS consistently delivers the best results compared to the other algorithms.

8 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented our work on integrating systematic preventive maintenance (PM) policies into hybrid flow shop scheduling to minimize makespan. We assumed that machines could be periodically unavailable during the production process, and the criteria used were simple yet effective. More importantly, these criteria are adaptable to a wide range of scheduling problems, addressing a key gap in the integration of existing techniques in the literature.

To solve this complex problem, we proposed a multi-agent-based artificial immune system (MAS AIS) algorithm, incorporating advanced operators such as uniform set crossover and single-point mutation. Additionally, we evaluated adaptations of several well-known heuristics, including Branch and Bound, SPT, Genetic Algorithm, and Reinforcement Learning.

A comprehensive benchmark was established, featuring up to 180 jobs and 9 stages, to evaluate the performance of the algorithms. The results demonstrated that MAS AIS consistently delivered satisfactory outcomes compared to other algorithms, while also proving its robustness across the three PM policies.

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